

PSSOH

Revitalizing old tablets/laptops with Linux operating system

Nebojša Jovanović

About Linux OS

- Open-source, safe, reliable OS
- Can be installed on pretty much everything

Linux installed on a toaster
by a [Reddit user](#)

What Linux distro to choose?

Xubuntu!

- **Lightweighth** official Ubuntu flavour
- Perfect for older hardware
- Great balance between resources and features
- Minimum requirements:
 - 512 Mb of RAM
 - 8 GB of storage
 - monitor capable of at least 800×600 pixels resolution.

Beginner-friendly

Intermediate

Hard mode

Installation process

- Check the requirements for you hardware and choose the distro accordingly
- Feel free to experiment

Ubuntu

Based on Debian

Mint

Based on Ubuntu

elementary OS

Based on Ubuntu (LTS)

Zorin

Based on Ubuntu

Solus

[Independent]

Garuda Linux

Based on Arch

EndeavourOS

Based on Arch

Manjaro

Based on Arch

MX Linux

Based on Debian

Fedora

Based on Red Hat

OpenSUSE

[Independent]

Arch

[Independent] – DIY

Gentoo

[Independent] – DIY

Slackware

[Independent]

Linux From Scratch

[Independent] – DIY

Qubes OS

Based on Fedora – Security

NixOS

[Independent] – DIY

- When you are set, go to the distro official download page
- Recommended to download the latest LTS release

Download Xubuntu

Latest LTS release: 20.04, Focal Fossa

The 20.04 release, codenamed Focal Fossa, is a **Long Term Support** release and has support for 3 years. To learn more about the release, please refer to the [release announcement](#), which has links to complete release notes as well as highlights of the improvements in the release.

Torrent downloads

If you know how to use torrents, it is highly recommended and preferred to use torrent downloads.

[64-bit systems >](#)

- Create a bootable USB stick

[Rufus](#)

[Etcher](#)

- Plug in and access **BIOS** on your device
- Check the correct keys for your specific manufacturer and laptop

Boot Menu Keys

Boot Menu	Diagnostics	Startup Device	BIOS
F12	F12 select diags	F12	F2

Boot Menu	Diagnostics	Startup Device	BIOS
Esc	F2	F9	F10

Boot Menu	Diagnostics	Startup Device	BIOS
F12 (some Enter)	Boot from flash drive	Enter	F1

Boot Menu	Diagnostics	Startup Device	BIOS
Desktop F8 Laptop Esc	NA	Desktop F8 Laptop Esc	Desktop Del Laptop F2 or Del

Boot Menu	Diagnostics	Startup Device	BIOS
Esc F12 F9	NA	F12 (some) (if enabled)	Del F2

Boot Menu	Diagnostics	Startup Device	BIOS
F12	NA	NA	F1 Esc F2 F12

Boot Menu	Diagnostics	Startup Device	BIOS
Esc F10	NA	NA	F1 Esc F2 F12

Picture was taken from
<http://kb.naturalnetworks.com/article/boot-menu-keys-314.html>

English

Español

Esperanto

Euskara

Français

Gaeilge

Galego

Hrvatski

Íslenska

Italiano

Kurdî

Latviski

Lietuviškai

Magyar

Nederlands

No localization (UTF-8)

Try Xubuntu

Install Xubuntu

You can try Xubuntu without making any changes to your computer, directly from this CD.

Or if you're ready, you can install Xubuntu alongside (or instead of) your current operating system. This shouldn't take too long.

Keyboard layout

www.linuxhu22.com

Choose your keyboard layout:

- English (Australian)
- English (Cameroon)
- English (Ghana)
- English (Nigeria)
- English (South Africa)
- English (UK)
- English (US)**
- Esperanto

- English (US)**
- English (US) - Cherokee
- English (US) - English (Colemak)
- English (US) - English (Dvorak)
- English (US) - English (Dvorak, alt. intl.)
- English (US) - English (Dvorak, intl., with dead keys)
- English (US) - English (Dvorak, left-handed)
- English (US) - English (Dvorak, right-handed)

Type here to test your keyboard

Detect Keyboard Layout

Quit

Back

Continue

Updates and other software

Download updates while installing Xubuntu

This saves time after installation.

Install third-party software for graphics and Wi-Fi hardware and additional media formats

This software is subject to license terms included with its documentation. Some is proprietary.

Quit

← Back

Continue

- Best to do your own partition scheme

Installation type www.linuxbuzz.com

This computer currently has no detected operating systems. What would you like to do?

- Erase disk and install Xubuntu
Warning: This will delete all your programs, documents, photos, music, and any other files in all operating systems.
- Encrypt the new Xubuntu installation for security
You will choose a security key in the next step.
- Use LVM with the new Xubuntu installation
This will set up Logical Volume Management. It allows taking snapshots and easier partition resizing.

- Something else**
You can create or resize partitions yourself, or choose multiple partitions for Xubuntu.

Device	Type	Mount point	Format?	Size	Used	System
/dev/sda						

+ - Change...

New Partition Table... Revert

Device for boot loader installation:

/dev/sda ATA VBOX HARDDISK (41.9 GB) ▼

- Boot partition - contains the boot loader

- Home partition - personal files

- System partition - root

- Swap - to compensate for lower RAM

Write the changes to disks?

If you continue, the changes listed below will be written to the disks. Otherwise, you will be able to make further changes manually.

The partition tables of the following devices are changed:
SCSI3 (0,0,0) (sda)

The following partitions are going to be formatted:
partition #1 of SCSI3 (0,0,0) (sda) as ext4
partition #5 of SCSI3 (0,0,0) (sda) as ext4
partition #6 of SCSI3 (0,0,0) (sda) as ext4
partition #7 of SCSI3 (0,0,0) (sda) as swap

Go Back

Continue

/dev/sda ATA VBOX HARDDISK (41.9 GB)

Your name: ✓

Your computer's name: ✓

The name it uses when it talks to other computers.

Pick a username: ✓

Choose a password: **Strong password**

Confirm your password: ✓

- Log in automatically
- Require my password to log in

Welcome to Xubuntu

Start exploring your new desktop by making yourself familiar with the applications menu.

Use the Software application to install more applications and the Settings Manager to customise the look and feel of your desktop.

- The idea for this workshop was formed when we installed Linux Xubuntu 20.01 on **ASUS T100 transformer book**
- **Windows 8** is native OS on this tablet
- Hardware is suited to work with Windows 8

The main problem was the old 32 BIOS on this tablet, which is not supported by the 64 bit boot loader

Solution?

- **Linux community!**
- One of the best in the world
- Since the platform is open-source many developers are fixing the most various types of problems

1. <https://www.linux.org/forums/>
2. <https://ubuntu.com/community>
3. <https://www.linuxquestions.org/>

LINUX.ORG

Forums ▾

What's new ▾

Linux Tutorials ▾

Members ▾

Download Linux

Newsletter

Credits ▾

<https://github.com/jfwells/linux-asus-t100ta>

master 1 branch 0 tags

Go to file Add file Code

jfwells Moved from deprecated v4l2_mbus_pixelcode to media_bus_format. 4301c88 on Jan 9, 2016 34 commits

boot	wrong EFI	8 years ago
cm3218_ambient_light_sensor_driver	Updated README	8 years ago
kernel-compiled	Added compiled kernel	8 years ago
mt9m114-driver	Added ACPI support to driver	6 years ago
nvrnm/lib/firmware/brcm	Added latest patches	8 years ago
patches	Added latest patches	8 years ago
support-scripts	Update base-station.sh	6 years ago
video/usr/share/X11/xorg.conf.d	- Rotation script, rotates screen clockwise	8 years ago
webcam	Moved from deprecated v4l2_mbus_pixelcode to media_bus_format.	6 years ago
.config	added config	8 years ago
LICENSE	initial commit	8 years ago
README.md	Updated README	8 years ago

☰ README.md

linux-asus-t100ta

Getting Linux (Esp. Ubuntu) up and running well on the Asus Transformer T100

Look in the subfolders for various useful items.

About

Getting Linux (Esp. Ubuntu) up and running well on the Asus Transformer T100

📖 Readme

📄 GPL-2.0 License

Releases

No releases published

Packages

No packages published

Languages

master linux-asus-t100ta / boot / Go to file Add file ...

 jfwells wrong EFI 4721f7d on Mar 8, 2014 [History](#)

..

bootia32.efi	wrong EFI	8 years ago
readme.md	Added boot EFI	8 years ago

readme.md

- Xubuntu was successfully installed on ASUS T1000, and it has even fixed the notebook touchscreen problem!

Conclusion

- Don't throw your old laptops and tablets in the trash

Try Linux first!

Questions?

Email: nebojsa.php@gmail.com

Github: <https://github.com/nebojsa55>

